

INFLUENCES OF NEW MEDIA TREND AMONG JOURNALIST IN NEPAL

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Abstract

Social media's interactive features have transformed journalism into a forum for the exchange of ideas, with platforms like blogs, YouTube, Twitter, and Facebook playing increasingly vital roles in news dissemination. The value of the audience to the media has been reinforced by social media, not only as news sources, but also as news sensors. This research aimed to assess the effect of new media trend among journalists of Nepal. The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design, surveying 422 Nepalese journalists through snowball sampling. Face-to-face interviews covered demographics, journalism specifics, media usage, attitudes, perceptions, integration effects, challenges, and social media policies in media organizations. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 20, and a p-value below 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The study reveals a predominant presence of younger adults aged 21-30 years (68.3% male) with 70.3% married, holding Bachelor's (52.8%) and Master's (36.0%) degrees, indicating a diverse mix of professionals in journalism. It underscores a notable shift towards digital platforms in Nepalese journalism, with online news sites and social media playing pivotal roles in sourcing and disseminating stories, complementing traditional media. Despite challenges such as intensified competition and concerns regarding journalistic integrity, participants perceive positive impacts of media integration, including increased collaboration and enhanced news efficiency. Furthermore, it emphasizes the need for an online media policy for upholding professionalism and integrity in Nepalese journalism.

Keywords: *Influences, Journalists, Media Impact, New Media Trend, Nepal*

Introduction

Journalism is a long-established profession that is widely practiced throughout the world. Over the last ten years, the rise of social media has had a significant impact on the way news is reported and digested by all parties involved in journalism with traditional journalists taking on a developed role that includes using social media to both deliver and promote their work (Thomas, 2013). The internet began as a collection of newsgroups where people could read and post (Alejandro, 2010). The rise of the internet and mobile apps as popular news consumption

channels has profoundly altered what constitutes journalism (Pradhan & Kumari, 2018). Social media's interactive features have transformed journalism into a forum for the exchange of ideas, with platforms like blogs, YouTube, Twitter, and Facebook playing increasingly vital roles in news dissemination (Poell & Borra, 2011). Web platforms prioritize speed, leading journalism to prioritize quantity over quality, relying less on fieldwork and research, while technological tools enable faster production, shifting focus to form and fostering collaboration between journalists and audiences in news creation (Alejandro, 2010; Pradhan & Kumari, 2018).

The invention of information and communication technology, because the internet has enabled people to learn about events without physically attending them. Journalists can report on breaking news from all over the world via the internet (Alice, 2013). The value of the audience to the media has been reinforced by social media, not only as news sources, but also as news sensors. Users of the social messaging service Twitter have taken on the role of social news sensors in the case of rapidly developing breaking news events such as natural disasters (Sakaki et al., 2010). Local cable television networks have broadened their audience to a global scale, and concurrently, terrestrial and satellite TV stations in Nepal have undergone a transition to online platforms (Dahal, 2023). The present study aimed to investigate the effects of new media trends in Nepal.

Nepali journalism has grown rapidly with many media outlets since 1990, leading to diverse content and expanded coverage, but also creating chaos in news media environment due to the simultaneous development of various genres (Acharya & Sharma, 2022). With social media surpassing traditional media, journalists in Kathmandu face the challenge of adapting to intensified competition while maintaining journalistic standards and leveraging social media's strengths for effective communication (Dahal, 2023). Thus, the present study aimed to investigate the effects of new media trends among journalists available all over Nepal.

Methodology

The study utilized a descriptive cross-sectional design employing a quantitative research approach, selecting 422 journalists of Nepal through snow ball sampling method. Face to face interviews was conducted of the participants covering demographics, journalism details, media platforms/tools, journalist attitudes, impact perceptions, media integration effects, challenges with new media, and social media policies in media organizations. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 20, and a p-value below 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Descriptive statistics were employed to depict participant demographics and customer satisfaction, including mean, standard deviation, and percentages. Bivariate analysis, aligned with research objectives, utilized a Chi-square test to identify associated factors.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Respondent's Profile

Statement		Frequency (N)	Percent (%)
Age (years)	21-30	252	60.4
	31-40	128	30.7
	41-50	37	8.9
Sex	Male	285	68.3

	Female	132	31.7
Marital status	Married	293	70.3
	Single	116	27.8
	Divorced	8	1.9
Education level (completed)	Secondary level (class 9-12)	47	11.3
	Bachelor	220	52.8
	Masters and above	150	36.0
Duration of Journalism Career	Less than 1 year	28	6.7
	1-5 years	116	27.8
	5-10 years	128	30.7
	10-15 years	68	16.3
	More than 15 years	77	18.5
Current Media Affiliation	Print newspaper/magazine	148	35.5
	Online news site	149	35.7
	Television	60	14.4
	Radio	60	14.4
Primary Beat/Area of Focus	Political Affairs	56	13.4
	Social Affairs	72	17.3
	Business and Economy	29	7.0
	Education	47	11.3
	Health	16	3.8
	Multiple categories	197	47.2

Table 1 presents the distribution of participants based on various demographic factors, a majority of participants aged 21-30 (60.4%), predominantly male (68.3%), and mostly married (70.3%). Education levels varied with 52.8% holding a bachelor's degree and 36.0% having completed a master's degree or higher.

The data reveals that many journalists have 1-5 years (27.8%) and 5-10 years (30.7%) of experience. Media affiliations are evenly split between print newspapers/magazines (35.5%) and online news sites (35.7%), with smaller percentages in television (14.4%) and radio (14.4%). Primary beats vary, with focus on political affairs (13.4%), social affairs (17.3%), education (11.3%), and a large number covering multiple categories (47.2%).

Table 2: Media Platforms and Tools Used by Journalists

Statement		Frequency (N)	Percent (%)
Media Platforms Used for Sourcing and Researching Stories	Print newspapers/magazines	189	45.3
	Online news sites	273	65.5
	Social media (e.g. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram)	221	53.0
	News wires (e.g. Reuters, AP)	64	15.3
Media Platforms Utilized for Disseminating	Print newspapers/magazines	187	44.8
	Online news sites	234	56.1
	Social media (e.g. Twitter, Facebook,	112	26.9

Stories	Instagram)		
	Broadcast (TV, radio)	124	29.7
Frequency of Social Media Use for News Sharing	Several times a day	239	57.3
	Once a day	86	20.6
	A few times a week	56	13.4
	Rarely or never	36	8.6
Preferred Tools for Recording Audio Interviews	A smartphone voice recorder app	198	47.5
	A digital audio recorder	183	43.9
	A cassette tape recorder	8	1.9
	A Dictaphone	20	4.8
	Camera	8	1.9
Utilization of Tools and Software in Journalism Work	Content management systems (CMS)	88	21.1
	Video/audio editing software	297	71.2
	Data analysis tools (e.g. Excel, R)	104	24.9
	Social media management tools (e.g. Hootsuite, Tweet deck)	56	13.4

Table 2 outlines the media platforms and tools utilized by journalists for sourcing, researching, and disseminating stories. For sourcing and researching stories, online news sites (65.5%) and social media (53.0%) are highly utilized, along with print newspapers/magazines (45.3%) and news wires (15.3%). In disseminating stories, online news sites (56.1%) and print newspapers/magazines (44.8%) are prominent, alongside social media (26.9%) and broadcast (29.7%). Moreover, the frequency of social media use for news sharing varies, with several times a day being the most common (57.3%). In terms of preferred tools, smartphone voice recorder apps (47.5%) and digital audio recorders (43.9%) are frequently used for recording audio interviews, while video/audio editing software (71.2%) and data analysis tools (24.9%) are commonly utilized in journalism work.

Table 3: Attitudes and Social Media Policy/Guideline for Journalists

Attitudes Statement		Frequency (N)	Percent (%)
Perceived Importance of Journalists' Activity on Social Media	Very important	381	91.4
	Somewhat important	36	8.6
Impact of Social Media on Journalistic Work	Yes	353	84.7
	No	16	3.8
	Unsure	48	11.5
Sources of Information on New Media and Journalism Tools	Attending conferences or workshops	252	60.4
	Reading industry publications or websites	193	46.3
	Networking with colleagues	169	40.5
	Experimenting with new tools and technologies	182	43.6
Journalists' Training in Media Platforms and Tools	Yes	236	56.6
	No	181	43.4

Statement on Social Media Policy/Guideline			
Existence of Social Media Policy	Yes	288	69.1
	No	85	20.4
	Unsure	44	10.6
Familiarity with Social Media Policy	Very familiar	288	69.1
	Somewhat familiar	80	19.2
	Not very familiar	49	11.8
Topics Addressed in Social Media Policy	Personal use of social media	252	60.4
	Professional use of social media	239	57.3
	Posting content on social media	128	30.7
	Interacting with sources and subjects on social media	134	32.1
	Responding to comments and messages on social media	96	23.0
Perceived Effectiveness of Social Media Policy/Guideline	Very effective	316	75.8
	Somewhat effective	72	17.3
	Not very effective	16	3.8
	Not at all effective	5	1.2
	Unsure	8	1.9
Incidents of Action Against Violation of Social Media Policy	Yes	279	66.9
	No	62	14.9
	Unsure	76	18.2

The table 3 data indicates that journalists perceive their activity on social media as highly important, with 91.4% considering it very important. A majority (84.7%) acknowledge the impact of social media on their journalistic work. For sourcing information on new media and journalism tools, attending conferences or workshops (60.4%) and reading industry publications or websites (46.3%) are common methods. Additionally, many journalists (56.6%) have received training in media platforms and tools, highlighting their readiness to adapt to technological advancements in their profession.

Table presents data on social media policies/guidelines for journalists. A majority of respondents indicate the existence of a social media policy (89.5%), with many being very familiar with it (69.1%). These policies commonly address personal (60.4%) and professional (57.3%) use of social media, as well as posting content (30.7%), interacting with sources (32.1%), and responding to comments (23.0%). The perceived effectiveness of these policies is generally high, with 93.1% finding them at least somewhat effective. Additionally, a significant number report incidents of action against violations of the social media policy (81.8%). This data underscores the importance and prevalence of social media policies in guiding journalistic conduct in the digital age.

Table 4: Perception, Effects and Challenges of Media Integration in Journalists

Statements	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Perception										
I believe that social media have changed journalism practice.	168	40.3	220	52.8	29	7.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
New media technologies have made it easier for journalists to report on stories from remote or hard-to-reach areas in Nepal.	167	40.0	177	42.4	37	8.9	24	5.8	12	2.9
New media technologies have made it easier for citizen journalists to report on news in Nepal.	183	43.9	177	42.4	57	13.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
New media technologies have created new opportunities for media organizations in Nepal to collaborate and share resources.	175	42.0	201	48.2	41	9.8	0	0.0	0	0.0
Positive effects										
Increased opportunities for collaboration with other journalists/media outlets	115	27.6	250	60.0	24	5.8	28	6.7	0	0.0
Increased access to a wider range of sources and information	164	39.3	176	42.2	49	11.8	8	1.9	20	4.8
Increased speed and efficiency in gathering and disseminating news	167	40.0	181	43.4	49	11.8	20	4.8	0	0.0
Enhanced multimedia storytelling capabilities	207	49.6	153	36.7	29	7.0	8	1.9	20	4.8
Negative effects										
Increased pressure to produce content quickly and continuously	156	37.4	204	48.9	37	8.9	20	4.8	0	0.0
Decreased emphasis on in-depth reporting and investigative journalism	217	52.0	156	37.4	16	3.8	0	0.0	28	6.7
Increased competition for audience attention	163	39.1	178	42.7	56	13.4	20	4.8	0	0.0
Increased prevalence of sensationalism and click bait headlines	160	38.4	180	43.2	57	13.7	0	0.0	20	4.8
Challenges										
I find difficulty in verifying information.	171	41.0	217	52.0	29	7.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
The pressure has increased to produce content quickly and continuously.	171	41.0	214	51.3	24	5.8	0	0.0	8	1.9

I find difficulty in separating fact from opinion or propaganda.	160	38.4	184	44.1	57	13.7	16	3.8	0	0.0
I find difficulty in identifying credible sources.	196	47.0	154	36.9	51	12.2	8	1.9	8	1.9
I find difficulty in maintaining objectivity and impartiality.	155	37.2	200	48.0	54	12.9	8	1.9	0	0.0
Social media affected the practice of journalism.	151	36.2	217	52.0	33	7.9	0	0.0	16	3.8
The need for journalists to constantly adapt to new media technologies affected their job satisfaction.	184	44.1	168	40.3	45	10.8	8	1.9	12	2.9
The need for journalists to constantly adapt to new media technologies affected their job security.	176	42.2	204	48.9	37	8.9	0	0.0	0	0.0

Table 4 shows participants' perceptions of journalism practice impact. A significant majority believe social media has changed journalism (92.3%), new media aids reporting from remote areas (82.4%) and enables citizen journalists (86.3%), and facilitates collaboration among media organizations (90.2%), underscoring the transformative role of new media in Nepali journalism.

The table outlines the effects of media integration on journalistic work as perceived by participants. Positively, a majority agree that media integration has increased opportunities for collaboration with other journalists or media outlets (87.6%), broadened access to a wider range of sources and information (81.5%), enhanced speed and efficiency in gathering and disseminating news (83.4%), and improved multimedia storytelling capabilities (86.3%).

Conversely, participants also acknowledge negative impacts, with a significant proportion noting increased pressure to produce content quickly and continuously (86.3%), a decrease in emphasis on in-depth reporting and investigative journalism (89.4%), heightened competition for audience attention (81.8%), and a rise in sensationalism and clickbait headlines (81.6%).

The table outlines the challenges faced by journalists due to new media technologies. A substantial proportion of respondents express difficulty in verifying information (93.0%), feeling pressure to produce content quickly and continuously (92.3%), and identifying credible sources (83.9%). Additionally, many journalists find it challenging to separate fact from opinion or propaganda (82.5%) and maintain objectivity and impartiality (85.2%). Social media's impact on journalism is recognized, with a majority agreeing that it has affected journalistic practices (88.2%). Furthermore, a significant number believe that the constant need to adapt to new media technologies affects both job satisfaction (84.4%) and job security (91.1%). These findings highlight the multifaceted challenges journalists encounter in navigating the evolving landscape of new media.

Table 5: Extent of Coverage in Media Organization's Social Media Policy/Guideline

Aspects	Completely		Great Extent		Some Extent		Small Extent		Not At All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Professionalism	224	53.7	120	28.8	45	10.8	8	1.9	20	4.8
Accuracy	256	61.4	80	19.2	53	12.7	28	6.7	0	0.0
Confidentiality	256	61.4	72	17.3	73	17.5	16	3.8	0	0.0
Privacy	256	61.4	47	11.3	53	12.7	53	12.7	8	1.9
Fairness	228	54.7	107	25.7	38	9.1	8	1.9	36	8.6

Table 5 outlines the extent of coverage in media organization's social media policies/guidelines regarding various aspects. The data indicates that a substantial proportion of respondents believe professionalism (82.5%), accuracy (80.6%), confidentiality (78.7%), privacy (74.1%), and fairness (80.4%) are covered to a great extent or completely in their organization's policies. This suggests a strong emphasis on incorporating these key elements into social media guidelines, highlighting the importance of upholding journalistic standards and ethical considerations in the digital realm.

Discussion

The present study highlights a shift towards digital platforms like online news sites and social media for sourcing and disseminating stories, alongside the continued relevance of traditional media. This closely aligned with (Mahaseth & Qureshi, 2021) study, highlighting the transformative shift from traditional to online models in Nepal, emphasizing the need for an online media policy to ensure positive utilization of technology, and suggesting that both models can complement each other for optimal outcomes despite their respective pros and cons. Social media plays a pivotal role in news sharing, as emphasized by Acharya et al. (2012) because social media is important tool for journalists for reporting, and promoting news. While preferences for smartphone apps and digital recorders indicate modern trends in audio interview recording, reflecting an evolving landscape of journalism practices.

Participants overwhelmingly believe journalists' social media activity as crucial, with 84.7% recognizing social media's impact on journalism, which correspondence with the findings of (Acharya et al., 2012). Attitudes toward social media integration and new media technologies vary in Nepal, with recognition of the importance of information sources like conferences, industry publications, and websites, alongside a notable lack of training in media platforms and tools, suggesting a potential skills gap, as noted by Alice (2013) and Mahaseth & Qureshi (2021) study. Alongside accelerated news dissemination and increased availability, challenges such as intensified competition are noted, emphasizing the complexity of Nepal's media landscape and the necessity for adaptive strategies to effectively navigate challenges and leverage opportunities. Despite all theses, the efficiency of journalists has been boosted by social media, with a significant portion of them employing these platforms not only to gather news but also for various other purposes (Alice, 2013).

Participants' perceive a transformation in journalism driven by social media and new media technologies, as highlighted by the findings of Mahaseth & Qureshi (2021) study. Opinions on new media technologies vary, acknowledging effectiveness in remote reporting, facilitation of citizen journalism, and opening opportunities for collaboration within media organizations.

Journalists in Southeast Asian nation are adopting Facebook for their reporting, comprehending their audience, and establishing their brand (Vu et al., 2020). The study reveals that media integration positively impacts journalism, fostering increased collaboration, expanded source access, enhanced news efficiency, and improved multimedia storytelling. This is highlighted by the Stepanov (2019) study as modern technology reshapes journalism, driving traditional media to adopt online platforms for faster, more diverse, and interactive content. Respondents express concerns about media integration, noting increased pressure for rapid content production and a diminished focus on in-depth reporting, signaling shifts in journalistic priorities and integrity. This is emphasized by Ghimire (2020) study, where Nepalese media exhibit sensationalism for profit and audience appeal, breaking monopolies and shaping public opinion, while online platforms prioritize clickbait over quality reporting, emphasizing the need for improved oversight and integrity in information dissemination.

The challenges faced by journalists in the era of new media indicates consensus on difficulties in verifying information, increased pressure to produce content quickly, struggles in distinguishing fact from opinion, challenges in identifying credible sources, and the transformative impact of social media on journalism. Though, digital media is boon for journalism but journalists still face professional hurdles like gatekeeping concerns, swift information updates, and moderating content after publication. (Babcock, 2012; Friend & Singer, 2015; Heikkilä et al., 2018). But, a significant trend observed among the majority of traditional media outlets in Nepal is the practice of republishing or rebroadcasting content already disseminated in their online portals or conventional platforms (Acharya, 2014). Adaptation to new media technologies affects job satisfaction and security, with significant agreement among respondents. Thus, to effectively utilize communication technology, journalists are required to have proficiency, expertise, and understanding in various areas, including computer literacy, information literacy, media literacy, visual literacy, among others (as cited in Nwanne (2016) study).

Hence, the study highlights the presence of social media policies within respondents' organizations, emphasizing professionalism, accuracy, confidentiality, privacy, and fairness, underlining the significance of managing online communication in journalism. Likewise, Acharya (2012) study underscores the necessity of establishing an online media policy in Nepal to leverage technology for promoting positive societal changes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study on influences of new media effects among journalists in Nepal provides valuable insights, reflecting the evolving landscape of journalism. The research findings underscore a notable shift towards digital platforms in Nepalese journalism, with online news sites and social media playing pivotal roles in sourcing and disseminating stories, complementing traditional media. Despite challenges such as intensified competition and concerns regarding journalistic integrity, participants perceive positive impacts of media integration, including increased collaboration and enhanced news efficiency. However, there are noted challenges in verifying information and maintaining journalistic standards amidst the rapid evolution of digital media. Establishing robust social media policies is crucial for upholding professionalism and integrity in journalism, aligning with calls for an online media policy in Nepal to navigate the transformative effects of technology on societal communication.

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